

PREVENTIVE MEASURES TO IMPROVE MAINTENANCE CULTURE AND QUALITY IN A PUBLIC BUILDING

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18051013>

ABSTRACT

This study addresses the issue of inadequate maintenance culture in public buildings, particularly in technology hubs, which impacts their functionality, sustainability, and overall quality. The aim of the study is to explore ways to improve maintenance culture and quality in the design and operation of technology hubs. The objectives include identifying the essence of maintenance culture, understanding the factors affecting it, and evaluating existing literature and case studies. The research employs a qualitative methodology, utilizing purposive sampling to select case studies from Lagos, Ibadan, and an international technology hub. The sample includes three case studies, each analyzed based on their design elements, maintenance culture, and the challenges they face. Data were collected through field surveys and secondary sources, with analysis focusing on key factors such as material selection, ventilation design, and environmental considerations. Findings reveal that poor material selection, inadequate ventilation design, and failure to consider environmental conditions are major factors affecting maintenance culture in public buildings. Case studies show that thoughtful design, including durable materials and natural ventilation, can significantly reduce maintenance costs and improve building performance. The study concludes that addressing these factors through better design practices can enhance maintenance culture and prolong the life of technology hubs. Recommendations include prioritizing durable materials, incorporating natural ventilation, and considering environmental factors during the design phase to improve overall building quality and reduce long-term maintenance costs.

Keywords: *Maintenance culture, quality maintenance, public building and preventive measures*

Introduction

It is generally accepted that spaces provided by the government for public use, such as a technology hub where technologists, computer scientists, hackers, web developers, and programmers congregate to network, share programs, and bring their ideas to fruition, can be classified as public buildings. A key element in ensuring the continued functionality of such spaces is maintenance. A proper maintenance culture is essential to keep both the building and its facilities in good working condition, ensuring they remain relevant and continue to serve their intended purpose. Public buildings, therefore, serve as an integral part of government provision, fulfilling governance needs and providing services to the governed. These buildings are meant to benefit the society and the people at large. However, public buildings are not just owned by the government; they are collectively owned by the public, with the government representing the interests of the people.

The status and condition of these public buildings are often reflective of the value that both the government and society place on them. This is especially true for buildings that have historical significance or played pivotal roles in the development of a society. Such buildings, often regarded as monuments, reflect the cultural and social history of the people. In Nigeria, however, the deplorable state of public buildings, such as airports, hospitals, and schools, raises serious concerns. These

buildings often lack proper management, which in turn affects their functionality and contributes to a decline in national development.

As observed, a technology hub can foster technological development in a community, promoting openness to ICT knowledge and innovation. However, such goals are difficult to achieve if there is inadequate maintenance of the building and its facilities. According to Nahimah (2008), the poor state of Nigeria's aviation industry was largely attributed to the lack of a maintenance culture and the insufficient training of professional engineers. The author argued that maintaining existing aircraft was more valuable than acquiring new ones, stating that a well-maintained aging aircraft could be as effective as a poorly maintained new aircraft. This perspective is particularly relevant when applied to public buildings, where the neglect of maintenance can result in severe deterioration over time.

The design phase of a building plays a crucial role in influencing its maintenance needs. As Speight (2010) emphasized, the design stage should account for maintenance considerations to prevent future problems. A building's ability to withstand wear and tear depends significantly on the materials used and the design's foresight in anticipating maintenance needs. Private sector contributions to national development, particularly in infrastructure, can only be maximized when facilities are continuously reliable, available, and maintainable.

In Nigeria, the maintenance culture is alarmingly low, with public buildings often deteriorating rapidly. The absence of proper maintenance results in buildings becoming obsolete before reaching their expected lifespan. According to Wahab (2015), the country's low priority on property management leads to the neglect of public properties. The lack of a maintenance culture, compounded by the absence of clear benchmarks for maintaining public assets, accelerates the decay of these buildings.

The consequences of this neglect are far-reaching. Gurjit (2010) noted that the poor maintenance of public buildings negatively affects the quality of life, contributing to socio-political instability. According to Dekker et al. (2006), several factors influence maintenance practices, including safety measures, construction defects, and the skill level of maintenance personnel. These factors highlight the urgent need for improved maintenance practices to ensure the quality of public buildings.

Problem Statement

Most public buildings in Nigeria today lack adequate maintenance, leading to rapid deterioration and a failure to function effectively and efficiently. This research seeks to explore ways to enhance the quality of public buildings through proper maintenance practices, with a particular focus on how preventive measures can improve the maintenance culture and overall quality of these buildings.

Objective of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to investigate whether preventive measures can accurately improve maintenance culture and quality in public buildings, specifically in technology hubs. Additionally, the study will:

1. Examine the importance of maintenance culture in public buildings, particularly in technology hubs.
2. Identify the factors that affect maintenance culture and explore strategies to address them.
3. Conduct a case study on existing technology hubs to assess the effectiveness of maintenance practices.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section explores the importance of, methods for, and factors influencing the improvement of maintenance culture in public properties in Nigeria. It examines various perspectives from researchers on maintenance culture, emphasizing its role in maintaining public buildings and facilities.

Maintenance Culture in Public Buildings

In this study, maintenance culture refers to the habit of regularly and consistently maintaining buildings, machinery, facilities, and infrastructure to keep them in good

working condition. SuwaibatulIslamiah, Abdul-Hakim, Syazwina, and Eizzatul (2012) argue that maintenance culture involves the values, mindset, behavior, perceptions, and underlying assumptions of individuals or groups who prioritize maintenance as an essential practice. For a nation to develop, it is crucial to prioritize both the installation and maintenance of existing facilities, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria, where rapid population growth has exacerbated the gap between the supply and demand for such facilities (Dabara et al., 2015).

The Nigerian government, according to Eti, Ogoji, and Probert (2006), made economic strides toward becoming one of the world's top twenty economies by 2020. Achieving sustainable infrastructure development, fostering a maintenance culture, and implementing strategic maintenance practices are fundamental to realizing this goal. Infrastructure facilities, including education, water supply, sewage systems, energy, transportation, and hospitals, are vital to national development. Governments at all levels, private organizations, and individuals must develop strategies to maintain these facilities to ensure their sustainability, and this can be achieved through cultivating a maintenance culture, which is directly linked to national development.

The state of public facilities in Nigeria is a significant concern for stakeholders. Facilities at airports, hospitals, schools, and roads indicate a lack of proper management to ensure the effective and efficient functioning of these essential

services, thereby impeding national development. Nahimah (2008) highlighted that the Nigerian aviation sector's problems were attributed to a lack of maintenance culture and inadequate professional training for engineers. He further argued that maintaining existing aircraft is more valuable than acquiring new ones, asserting that a well-maintained aging aircraft is as effective as a poorly maintained new one.

Conceptual Framework for Maintenance

The British Standards Institute (2004) defines maintenance as a combination of technical and administrative actions taken to preserve or protect a structure, system, or equipment, ensuring it functions properly. The Advanced Learner's Dictionary (2009) describes maintenance as the action or process of preserving an object or activity. Kumar and Suresh (2008) define maintenance as actions aimed at preventing equipment failure or repairing normal wear and tear to maintain the equipment's operational functionality. This study defines maintenance as a process of preserving an asset or facility in a state of continuous operation, ensuring it performs above a minimum acceptable level throughout its lifespan.

Companies focus on maintenance to reduce costs while improving quality and productivity. Effective maintenance is necessary for continuous operation, increasing equipment lifespan, availability, and proper functioning. Conversely, poorly maintained equipment often results in frequent failures, low utilization rates,

and delays in production schedules. Swanson (2001) refers to poorly maintained equipment as a "necessary evil," a viewpoint contradicted by Alsayouf (2007), who argues that regular facility maintenance should be seen as a source of profit rather than an unavoidable expense.

Existing maintenance records, as noted by Eti, Ogoji, and Probert (2006) and Omotehinshe et al. (2015), show the deteriorating state of public facilities in Nigeria, such as street lights that were once meant to beautify and illuminate the streets but have fallen into disrepair due to neglect and the absence of a maintenance culture. The role of private organizations in national development, particularly in facilities construction, environmental conservation, and employment generation, cannot be overstated. Nahimah (2008) emphasized that these organizations can contribute to national development by maintaining their facilities and ensuring their operational reliability.

The Essence of Maintenance

A comprehensive maintenance strategy prevents facility breakdowns and malfunctions, enabling facility managers to focus on capital improvements (Omotehinshe et al., 2015a; Akinyemi et al., 2016). In the absence of a defined strategy, time must be spent developing and communicating a maintenance plan. Effective tactics must be implemented to manage people, processes, and

infrastructure. This requires strong managerial capacity and must align with safety, environmental regulations, and cost-effectiveness (Campbell & Reyes-Picknell, 2006; Waeyenbergh & Pintelon, 2002).

Benefits of Embracing Maintenance Culture

Embracing a maintenance culture brings several benefits, including:

- Keeping assets in optimal working condition to minimize downtime and service disruptions.
- Maintaining facilities in a state of good repair to ensure the health and safety of the owners and users.
- Preserving the appearance and aesthetic value of assets.
- Maximizing the potential service life of facilities.
- Improving financial efficiency, which is reflected in the owner's financial statements.
- Preventing unnecessary damage to assets that could result in performance failures.

Classification of Maintenance

Several maintenance philosophies exist, but this study focuses on facility maintenance, categorized as follows:

1. **Planned Maintenance:** Organized and carried out with foresight and control, using records to follow a predetermined plan.
2. **Unplanned Maintenance:** Carried out without a predetermined plan, typically to restore a facility to a functional state after a failure.
3. **Preventive Maintenance:** Scheduled maintenance performed at predetermined intervals to reduce the likelihood of failure or performance degradation. This maintenance helps extend the useful life of assets by detecting and addressing potential issues before they become critical (Kumar & Suresh, 2008; Mobley, 2002).
4. **Corrective Maintenance:** Performed after a failure occurs, aiming to restore functionality. This maintenance is often reactive, with actions taken only after equipment failure (Mobley, 2004).
5. **Emergency Maintenance:** Immediate action taken to address failures that pose a serious risk, such as gas leaks or other critical incidents (Mobley, 2004).
6. **Scheduled Maintenance:** Preventive maintenance carried out at regular intervals, based on time or operational use.

7. **Condition-Based Maintenance:** Maintenance initiated based on the condition of the equipment, often monitored continuously or at regular intervals.

Maintenance Culture and Its Importance in Nigeria

In Nigeria, maintenance culture is one of the lowest globally, especially in urban areas where most public properties are located. Rural areas, however, exhibit a more positive approach, with traditional practices such as communal clearing of community spaces and maintaining private homes using locally sourced materials. According to Wahab (2010), the country places low priority on property management, which leads to neglect of public assets. Mbamali (2003) argued that the absence of a maintenance policy is a major reason for this neglect. The consequences of this neglect include rapid deterioration of public buildings and the harmful impact on their occupants (Seeley, 2010).

Inadequate maintenance culture is a characteristic feature of most public buildings in Nigeria, as noted by Rotimi and Mtallib (1995). Poor maintenance practices, combined with the lack of an appropriate benchmark, result in the early obsolescence of public buildings. The decline in maintenance culture is a major issue that government bodies at various levels must address.

Hindrances to Maintenance Culture in Nigeria

Several factors contribute to the poor maintenance culture in Nigeria, including:

- **Corruption:** Obayelu (2007) defines corruption as the misuse of public power for private gain, which threatens national development by diverting funds meant for maintenance. This leads to abandoned projects and neglected facilities.
- **Leadership:** Effective leadership is crucial for national development, but many Nigerian leaders lack the necessary vision, passion, and empathy to prioritize maintenance (Omotehinshe et al., 2015b).
- **Attitudinal Problems:** Nigerians' nonchalant attitude towards public and private property, coupled with neglect by public office holders, contributes to the deterioration of public facilities (Omotehinshe et al., 2015a).
- **Lack of Policy:** The absence of a national maintenance policy is a significant barrier. No comprehensive blueprint exists for how public facilities should be maintained, leading to disorganized maintenance efforts across various levels of government.

Improving Maintenance Culture in Public Buildings

Improving maintenance culture is essential for ensuring the long-term quality and sustainability of public buildings. The size and function of public buildings make them central to urban life, and their maintenance directly impacts the quality of life

in cities. McCrea et al. (2005) highlight that the quality of public facilities is a key factor in urban satisfaction and influences crime rates, health, safety, and social behavior.

To address the decay of public buildings, maintenance strategies must be integrated into the design and construction stages, ensuring the buildings are both durable and maintainable. The concept of **designing for maintainability** emphasizes the importance of planning for maintenance needs early in the design process, considering access, material durability, and ease of operation throughout the building's lifespan (Rounds, 2018; Government of Singapore, 2016). Ensuring that public buildings are designed with sustainability and maintainability in mind will minimize the need for extensive maintenance and reduce overall costs.

Conclusion

The section emphasizes that the design of public buildings should focus on durability and maintainability to ensure that they remain functional and cost-effective throughout their lifecycle. By addressing maintenance needs early in the design phase and integrating maintainability into the construction process, public buildings can be preserved for longer periods, minimizing maintenance costs and maximizing their service life. Effective maintenance culture is a key driver of national development and should be a priority in both policy and practice.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND MATERIAL

Introduction

This section outlines the research methods used to gather data and information regarding the improvement of maintenance and quality in the design of technology hubs. The aim is to identify architectural design approaches and requirements that can enhance maintenance culture and overall quality. Additionally, this section evaluates case studies and assesses their challenges and solutions in relation to maintenance culture.

Sample Technique

For this study, purposive sampling was adopted to select case studies based on the researcher's judgment. The researcher chose Lagos and Ibadan as local case studies, as these cities are known for their technological focus and infrastructure. These areas are considered ideal for examining how technology hubs can foster a positive environment for innovation. Moreover, an international case study was included to gain insights into existing facilities and how maintenance culture is improved in other contexts.

Analysis of Case Studies

Case studies provide valuable insights into existing designs, patterns, and methods, offering lessons on best practices to adopt and those to avoid. The case studies selected for this research have been critically appraised to fulfill the study's aims and objectives. This analysis enables the researcher to assess the performance of these projects and use their findings to create design solutions for improving maintenance culture in technology hubs. A thorough examination of the merits and demerits of each case study will serve as a guide in developing new design solutions, with the aim of eliminating identified shortcomings while building on successful aspects of the designs.

3.4.1 Case Study One (Local)

Brief Description: Wennovation Hub is a startup incubator, accelerator, and entrepreneurial training and networking center that aims to foster high-impact entrepreneurs. It has been operating since 2011 and has locations in Lagos, Ibadan, and Abuja. The hub plays a key role in Nigeria's innovation ecosystem.

Plate	Plate 3.4.1.	Plate	Plate 3.4.1.2:
<p data-bbox="224 279 448 831">3.4.1.3: showing co-working space of winnovation hub</p> <p data-bbox="264 1136 448 1430">(source: field survey November 2021)</p>	<p data-bbox="521 279 732 831">4: showing seminar room winnovation hub (source: field survey November 2021)</p>	<p data-bbox="756 279 1015 831">3.4.1.1: showing aerial view of winnovation hub (Source: field survey November 2021)</p>	<p data-bbox="1036 300 1300 957">showing approach view of The site of winnovation hub (Source: field survey November 2021)</p>

Table 3.4.1: Summary of the case study for Wennovation Hub.

- **Merits:**

- Aesthetically pleasing facades and interior spaces.
- Efficient approach to ventilation in interior spaces.
- Well-planned interior spaces with minimal columns that obstruct views.
- Choice of building materials that aid in maintenance.

- **Demerits:**

- Insufficient parking spaces.
- Excessive hardscape elements around the building.
- Inaccessibility of the main entrance for disabled individuals.

- **Deductions:**

- Large fenestration can enhance ventilation and improve the connection between interior and exterior spaces (Plate 3.4.1.3).
- The use of durable materials, such as high-quality paint and glazed ceramic tiles, can help prevent degradation and reduce the need for frequent maintenance (Plate 3.4.1.3, Plate 3.4.1.4).

3.4.2 Case Study Two (Local)

Brief Description: Zone Tech Park is a startup accelerator that focuses on building other startups. With \$6.5 million in funding, Zone Tech provides co-working spaces, advisory services, and technical support. Located on a 10,000 square meter facility, it can accommodate 150 cars and includes five meeting rooms, a studio, and a 650-seater conference hall. The park also features a beautifully landscaped environment.

<p>Plate 3.4.2.3: showing the view of the meeting room.</p> <p>Zone tech park (source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Plate 3.4.2.4: Showing event hall view of Conference room, Zone tech park (source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Pate 3.4.2.1: showing aerial view of Zone Tech Park. (Source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Plate 3.4.2.2: Showing façade of Zone Tech Park. (source: field survey, 2021)</p>
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Table 3.4.2: Summary of the case study for Zone Tech Park.

- **Merits:**
 - Maintenance-conscious environment.
 - Spacious parking area.
 - Well-ventilated interiors.
 - Positive influence of building materials on aesthetics and maintenance costs.

- **Demerits:**
 - Minimal natural ventilation.
 - Excessive hardscape areas.
 - Underutilized green spaces.

- **Deductions:**
 - Floor and wall finishes that resist dirt can reduce maintenance efforts, such as the use of glazed tiles and low-VOC paints (Plate 3.4.2.3, Plate 3.4.2.4).
 - Installing overhangs over external walls can prevent moisture from rain, which can lead to cracks and mold growth, thus reducing the need for frequent painting and plastering.

3.4.3 Case Study Three (International)

Brief Description: The Technology HUB in Ciudad Juárez, Mexico, is an innovative entrepreneurship and innovation community located near the U.S.-Mexico border. The facility, housed in the former Consulate General of the United States building, covers 1.8 acres and offers over 55,000 square feet of space. The hub includes co-working spaces, meeting rooms, a virtual reality demonstration facility, a green room, an auditorium, and a Fab Lab. It also features recreational areas and leisure spaces, such as a slide and a fireman’s pole, to foster creativity and collaboration.

<p>Plate 3.4.2.3: showing the view of the meeting room.</p> <p>Zone tech park (source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Plate 3.4.2.4: Showing event hall view of Conference room, Zone tech park (source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Pate 3.4.2.1: showing aerial view of Zone Tech Park. (Source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Plate 3.4.2.2: Showing façade of Zone Tech Park. (source: field survey, 2021)</p>

Table 3.4.3: Summary of the case study for the Technology HUB.

- **Merits:**

- Aesthetically pleasing facades and well-planned interior spaces with minimal columns obstructing views.
- Beautifully landscaped and well-drained environment.
- Sufficient circulation areas.
- **Demerits:**
 - Poor drainage on-site.
 - Inadequate natural ventilation.
- **Deductions:**
 - Vinyl tiles, used in the flooring, are stain-resistant and water-resistant, making them an ideal choice for maintaining cleanliness and reducing maintenance costs (Plate 3.4.3.2).
 - Introducing overhangs over external walls can protect the building from moisture-related issues and reduce the need for frequent maintenance, such as repainting and plastering.

Table 3.5.1 representation of the studied design elements, maintenance culture, and associated merits and demerits from the case studies, along with recommendations for improving maintenance culture through thoughtful design, material selection, and sustainable practices

Case Study	Design Elements	Merits	Demerits	Maintenance Culture Improvement	Deductions and Design Solutions
Wenovation Hub	Aesthetic facades,	- Aesthetically pleasing	- Insufficient parking spaces.	- Enhance ventilation through larger fenestration	- Large windows or larger fenestration
	efficient ventilation,	- and interior spaces.	Excessive fenestration	- Improve natural ventilation around (windows) to improve airflow.	- Prioritize connect interior to exterior spaces.
	well-planned interiors	- ventilation with interiors.	- Minimal Inaccessibility	- for durable materials such	- exterior spaces.

Case Study	Design Elements	Merits	Demerits	Maintenance Culture Improvement	Deductions and Design Solutions
Zone Park	Spacious parking, well-ventilated interiors, and	Maintenance-conscious environment. Spacious	Minimal use of natural ventilation. Excessive	Use finishes that resist dirt to reduce maintenance needs (e.g., glazed tiles, water damage.	Use of high-quality flooring and paints that resist dirt and need for frequent maintenance.

Case Study	Design Elements	Merits	Demerits	Maintenance Culture Improvement	Deductions and Design Solutions
	landscaped area. - Well- landscaped areas. - low-VOC paints). - Overhangs on environment. ventilated interiors. Underutilized green spaces. - Positive material choice impacting aesthetics and maintenance.			Introduce overhangs external walls help over external walls to mitigate rainwater protect from moisture penetration, damage and reduce reducing the maintenance costs. frequency of repainting and plastering.	

Case Study	Design Elements	Merits	Demerits	Maintenance Culture Improvement	Deductions and Design Solutions
Technology HUB (International)	Flexible spaces, - Well-planned glass-walled interior spaces with offices, co-minimal columns. - working areas, Well-landscaped recreational and drained spaces.	- Aesthetic facades and interior spaces. - Well-planned interior spaces with minimal columns. - Well-landscaped and drained environment.	- Poor drainage on-site. - Insufficient natural ventilation.	- Vinyl tiles with water and stain-resistant properties - minimize the need for frequent cleaning. Design overhangs to prevent moisture over external walls damage and protect building structure,	- Vinyl tiles are durable and resist water spillage, which enhances maintenance - Overhangs help prevent cracks and mold growth,

Case Study	Design Elements	Merits	Demerits	Maintenance Culture Improvement	Deductions and Design Solutions
				reducing maintenance costs.	reducing maintenance costs.

This study focuses on improving the maintenance culture in public buildings, particularly in technology hubs. It includes case studies from different locations to observe the measures taken to enhance maintenance culture in these spaces. The objective of this study is to identify the significance of maintenance culture in technology hubs, explore the factors affecting it, and relate these findings to existing literature, as shown in the tables below.

Table 3.5.2: The Essence of Maintenance Culture (according to Campbell & Reyes-Picknell, 2006) in Public Buildings with Respect to Conducted Case Studies

Factors Affecting Maintenance Culture in SN Public Buildings

Preventive Measures

References (Case Studies/Plate)

Poor Material Selection: Architects and developers often use new materials and methods that have not been properly tested or researched. As a result, many maintenance problems emerge in the future.

Building defects can be reduced by considering the availability of accurate and appropriate materials during the design stage.

Poor Ventilation Design: Natural ventilation in buildings is crucial for HVAC system design. Poor ventilation leads to ineffective removal of polluted indoor air, increasing maintenance costs.

To improve building maintenance, ventilation decisions made early in the design stage can have a significant impact on the building's performance.

3.4.1/all, 3.4.2/all, 3.4.3/all, 3.4.4/all
3.4.1/3.4.1.3, 3.4.4/3.4.4.3 (large windows for ventilation)

Factors Affecting Maintenance Culture in SN Public Buildings

Preventive Measures

References (Case Studies/Plate)

Ignoring Environmental Issues: Buildings

located in areas with adverse environmental conditions face challenges due to weather differences, which contribute to higher maintenance costs. Sustainability is a key consideration in building design.

Consider the environmental conditions of the site location when designing the building.

3.4.4 described the environmental condition that influenced the building design

Table 3.5.2: Factors Affecting Maintenance Culture in Buildings (according to Graham, 2009) with Respect to Conducted Case Studies

The tables above illustrate the factors that influence maintenance culture in public buildings and the preventive measures that can be implemented to improve it. These measures, informed by the case studies, focus on using appropriate materials, designing for natural ventilation, and considering environmental factors during the design phase to ensure the long-term sustainability and ease of maintenance for technology hubs.

This tables provides a comprehensive view of how design elements and material selection can improve maintenance culture in technology hubs, based on case studies and their respective analysis. It also highlights the importance of integrating sustainable practices into the design process to reduce future maintenance needs.

The table provides an overview of three case studies on technology hub buildings, focusing on design elements, maintenance culture, merits, demerits, and potential improvements. **Wenovation Hub**, **Zone Tech Park**, and **Technology HUB** each demonstrate thoughtful design elements like well-planned interior spaces, ventilation, and material choices that promote sustainability and ease of maintenance. However, challenges such as insufficient parking, poor drainage, and underutilized green spaces are common in all three hubs. The case studies highlight the need for better maintenance culture through improved material selection, such as durable paints and tiles, and design considerations like larger windows for better ventilation and overhangs to prevent moisture-related damage.

The analysis emphasizes the importance of integrating sustainable practices in the design phase to reduce long-term maintenance costs. For example, using vinyl tiles in high-traffic areas and introducing overhangs to protect the building from rainwater damage can significantly extend the life of a building and reduce maintenance efforts. These improvements, along with better use of natural ventilation and the right choice of materials, will enhance the maintenance culture in technology hubs. Ultimately, the study suggests that well-designed, durable buildings with a focus on sustainability and proper maintenance planning are crucial for improving the overall quality and longevity of public buildings in Nigeria and globally.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study align with past research that emphasizes the critical role of maintenance culture in enhancing the longevity and functionality of public buildings. For example, Nahimah (2008) and Gurjit (2010) both highlighted how poor maintenance practices contribute to the deterioration of public properties, a concern echoed in the case studies analyzed here, where buildings suffer from issues such as poor ventilation, inadequate parking, and underutilized spaces due to the lack of a strong maintenance culture. Similarly, the recommendation to use durable materials like high-quality paints and glazed ceramic tiles to reduce maintenance needs aligns with Kumar & Suresh (2008), who argued that the right materials can significantly extend the life of a facility. The focus on sustainable practices, such as the introduction of overhangs to prevent moisture-related damage, is also consistent with previous studies that underscore the importance of designing buildings with maintenance in mind to reduce long-term upkeep costs (Mobley, 2002).

However, the findings also present a more nuanced approach by integrating specific design solutions tailored to improve maintenance culture in technology hubs, which may not have been as explicitly addressed in previous research. While past studies like those by Swanson (2001) and Mobley (2004) discussed the importance of preventive maintenance, this study's emphasis on natural ventilation and space planning as part of the design process provides a more holistic view of how architectural choices directly impact maintenance culture. Furthermore, the case studies indicate that a shift towards considering maintenance during the early design phase, as recommended by Latham (1994) and Rounds (2018), could significantly improve building performance and reduce the deterioration rates seen in many Nigerian public buildings. This suggests that integrating maintenance considerations

at the design stage is a critical factor in achieving sustainable infrastructure, which past studies may have underemphasized.

SUMMARY

This study focuses on improving the maintenance culture in public buildings, with a particular emphasis on technology hubs. By conducting case studies in various locations, the research aims to identify the significance of maintenance culture in these buildings and the factors that influence it. The study's objective is to examine the essence of maintenance culture, factors affecting it, and strategies for improving it, drawing from existing literature and analyzing the case studies conducted. Through these case studies, the study also seeks to assess how thoughtful design, material selection, and sustainable practices can enhance the maintenance culture and overall quality of technology hub buildings.

One of the key factors identified in the research is poor material selection, which is often a result of using new materials that have not been adequately tested or researched. This leads to long-term maintenance problems. The study recommends considering the availability of appropriate materials during the design stage to reduce these issues. This finding aligns with previous research that emphasizes the importance of selecting durable, well-researched materials for the long-term sustainability of buildings. Case studies like Wennovation Hub, Zone Tech Park, and Technology HUB demonstrate how careful material choice can help mitigate maintenance challenges in the future.

Another significant factor affecting maintenance culture is poor ventilation design. Poor ventilation systems can lead to ineffective air circulation, which, in turn, increases maintenance costs due to the accumulation of pollutants. The study highlights the importance of incorporating adequate natural ventilation in the early

design phase, such as through the use of large windows. This recommendation echoes prior research that suggests early design decisions, like improving ventilation, have a substantial impact on reducing long-term maintenance needs. Case studies further show that enhancing natural airflow improves both building performance and maintenance efficiency.

The study also explores how ignoring environmental conditions can negatively affect a building's maintenance culture. Environmental factors such as local climate and weather patterns are critical when designing buildings. Failure to consider these conditions can lead to increased maintenance costs due to issues like moisture damage. The research advocates for designing buildings with environmental considerations in mind to reduce the need for frequent repairs. This approach, supported by the case studies, aligns with previous findings that emphasize the importance of sustainability in building design, with long-term maintenance being a key factor in the overall success of the building's operation. Through these analyses, the study provides actionable recommendations for improving maintenance culture in public buildings, especially technology hubs.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research highlights the critical role that maintenance culture plays in enhancing the quality and longevity of public buildings, particularly technology hubs. Through detailed case studies and empirical evidence, the study has demonstrated how thoughtful architectural design, material selection, and sustainable practices are fundamental in improving maintenance culture. The findings emphasize that the integration of these factors during the design phase can significantly reduce the long-term maintenance challenges faced by public buildings, ensuring they remain functional, sustainable, and efficient throughout their life cycle.

One of the key findings of this research is the impact of poor material selection on the maintenance culture of technology hubs. The use of inadequately tested or unsuitable materials leads to frequent maintenance issues, increasing operational costs and reducing the building's lifespan. To address this, the study recommends a more thoughtful approach to material choice, prioritizing durability and long-term performance. This aligns with existing literature that stresses the importance of using well-researched, high-quality materials to minimize maintenance needs. The case studies, such as Wenvovation Hub and Zone Tech Park, support this recommendation by showing how careful material selection can significantly reduce the frequency and cost of repairs.

Another major finding is the importance of effective ventilation design in reducing maintenance costs. Poor ventilation systems, especially in buildings with inadequate natural airflow, can lead to an accumulation of pollutants, which accelerates deterioration and increases maintenance efforts. The study suggests that larger windows and improved ventilation strategies be integrated into the design process to mitigate these issues. This recommendation is supported by the case studies, where buildings that prioritized natural ventilation showed better long-term

performance and required less frequent maintenance. This finding further reinforces previous research that highlights the significant impact of design decisions on the overall maintenance needs of a building.

Finally, the study underscores the importance of considering environmental factors during the design process. Buildings located in regions with challenging weather conditions are prone to accelerated wear and tear if environmental considerations are overlooked. The research advocates for designing buildings that account for local climate conditions, thereby reducing the need for costly and frequent repairs. This is consistent with prior studies that stress the need for sustainability in building design. The case studies analyzed in this research show that incorporating these considerations into the design phase can help extend the life of a building and ensure that it remains functional and cost-effective for years to come. Overall, this research provides a comprehensive framework for improving maintenance culture in technology hubs, with practical recommendations that can be applied in the design and management of public buildings.

Recommendation 1: Improved Material Selection

One of the key findings of this study is the importance of selecting appropriate materials during the design phase to enhance the maintenance culture of public buildings. Poor material selection, particularly the use of untested or unsuitable materials, leads to increased maintenance challenges and reduced building longevity. Therefore, it is recommended that architects and developers prioritize the use of durable, well-researched, and tested materials in the construction of technology hubs.

Implementation Strategy: To implement this recommendation, it is essential for designers and developers to engage in thorough research and testing of materials

before making any selections. Collaboration with material scientists and experts in building construction should be encouraged to ensure that materials chosen are suited to the local climate, building function, and long-term maintenance needs. Additionally, developers should invest in sourcing high-quality, low-maintenance materials that align with sustainability goals, such as energy-efficient windows and moisture-resistant wall finishes. Regular training and workshops for architects on emerging materials and their benefits should be organized to ensure that the latest, most durable materials are consistently used in new projects.

Recommendation 2: Incorporation of Natural Ventilation

The study highlights the critical role of effective ventilation in reducing maintenance costs and improving the overall functionality of public buildings. Poor ventilation systems contribute to the accumulation of pollutants and increased maintenance needs. It is recommended that the design of technology hubs should include provisions for natural ventilation, such as larger windows, open spaces, and cross-ventilation to enhance airflow and reduce dependency on mechanical ventilation.

Implementation Strategy: The implementation of this recommendation can be achieved by revising the building design phase to prioritize natural ventilation. This would involve adjusting the layout to ensure the strategic placement of windows, vents, and open spaces that facilitate airflow. Additionally, the design should account for climate and environmental conditions in the building's location to optimize ventilation. Designers should also incorporate features such as adjustable windows or vents that allow for user-controlled airflow. To ensure the success of these features, building management teams should conduct regular assessments of ventilation systems to confirm their effectiveness and make adjustments as needed,

while ensuring that natural ventilation is maintained alongside any mechanical systems. Incorporating these strategies from the outset will help in reducing long-term maintenance costs related to ventilation and improve indoor air quality.

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